
DN25: An adaptive quantum cryptography protocol for secure and efficient communication

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RESUMEN. La computación cuántica desafía las infraestructuras criptográficas clásicas y ha impulsado cuatro décadas de avances en protocolos de Distribución de Claves Cuánticas (QKD), desde BB84 hasta protocolos twin-field y multipartitos. No obstante, muchos esquemas actuales carecen de adaptabilidad frente a escenarios heterogéneos. Presentamos DN25, un protocolo criptográfico adaptativo que integra QKD, Criptografía Post-Cuántica (PQC) y modos híbridos, seleccionando dinámicamente el mecanismo más adecuado según las condiciones del sistema (capacidad de los dispositivos, distancia, rendimiento y requisitos de seguridad). DN25 busca equilibrar resistencia frente a adversarios cuánticos con eficiencia operacional en entornos restringidos o de alto rendimiento. Revisamos 20 protocolos QKD representativos, describimos la arquitectura de DN25 y esbozamos las consideraciones de prueba y evaluación.

Palabras clave. Cifrado Híbrido, Criptografía Cuántica, Negociación Dinámica, Protocolo Adaptativo, Seguridad Post-cuántica.

ABSTRACT. Quantum computing challenges classical cryptographic infrastructures and has driven four decades of development in Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) protocols, from BB84 to recent twin-field and multiparty schemes. However, many existing solutions lack adaptability across heterogeneous deployment scenarios. We introduce DN25, an adaptive cryptographic protocol that integrates QKD, Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC), and hybrid approaches, dynamically selecting the most suitable mechanism based on system conditions (device capabilities, distance, performance and security requirements). DN25 aims to balance robustness against quantum-enabled adversaries with operational efficiency in constrained or high-throughput environments. We review 20 representative QKD protocols, describe DN25's architecture, and outline testing and evaluation considerations.

Keywords. Adaptive Protocol, Dynamic Negotiation, Hybrid Encryption, Post-quantum Security, Quantum Cryptography.

1. Introduction

The development of quantum computing presents a profound challenge for modern cryptography, as widely used public-key schemes such as RSA and Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) can be broken by quantum algorithms [1]. To mitigate this risk, QKD has emerged as a method capable of providing information-theoretic security. Since the seminal contributions of Bennett and Brassard with BB84, Bennett's B92 protocol and Ekert's entanglement-based scheme, a wide spectrum of new protocols has been proposed. Among them, the Six-State protocol, SARG04, and decoy-state approaches have increased resilience to photon-number-splitting attacks. Further developments such as Differential-Phase-Shift

(DPS) protocols, Coherent-One-Way (COW), and Round-Robin DPS expanded practical optical implementations, while continuous-variable schemes, device-independent solutions and measurement-device-independent QKD improved robustness under more realistic conditions. In parallel, twin-field techniques, phase-matching approaches, floodlight QKD, satellite-based implementations and hybrid cryptographic designs demonstrated the potential for performance scalability and extended distance, ultimately pointing towards the foundations of a global quantum communication infrastructure [26].

Nevertheless, despite these advances, most QKD protocols remain constrained by static assumptions tailored to specific scenarios, presenting limitations when

considered in heterogeneous environments. Recent works illustrate both progress and ongoing challenges, such as space-ground communication, high-dimensional continuous-variable configurations, long-distance optical fiber links [21], and multiparty twin-field proposals [23]. As highlighted in contemporary surveys, the main difficulty is the absence of schemes capable of adapting their security mechanisms seamlessly to different contexts without introducing significant inefficiencies.

In order to address this gap, we propose DN25, an adaptive quantum cryptography protocol. The underlying idea of DN25 is to combine QKD, PQC, and hybrid models into a single flexible architecture. DN25 introduces an adaptive negotiation layer that dynamically selects the most suitable encryption mechanism according to contextual parameters such as channel quality, device constraints, and required security level. By doing so, DN25 preserves information-theoretic guarantees typical of QKD while ensuring elasticity and efficiency across a broad range of applications, from resource-constrained IoT devices to high-capacity data centers.

The contributions of this work are threefold: (i) it presents a structured analysis of 20 representative QKD protocols, spanning from the classical BB84 to more recent multiparty twin-field schemes, offering a comparative overview of their strengths, practical limitations, and open challenges in terms of scalability and device assumptions; (ii) it introduces DN25 as an adaptive cryptographic protocol that integrates QKD, PQC, and hybrid designs with context-aware elasticity, highlighting its ability to dynamically select the most efficient scheme depending on network conditions, device constraints, and security requirements; and (iii) it outlines an implementation pathway, providing initial considerations for simulation and experimental testing, while also identifying evaluation metrics.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the state of the art, reviewing 20 established quantum cryptography protocols in a comparative table. Section 3 details the methodology and architecture of DN25. Section 4 discusses anticipated results and insights. Finally, Section 5 concludes the article, summarizing findings and indicating directions for further research, while also highlighting the broader implications of adopting adaptive cryptographic approaches in future quantum communication networks.

2. State of the Art

Research on quantum cryptographic protocols has expanded significantly since their origins in the mid-1980s, and reviewing the state of the art provides a structured perspective on their evolution. This section surveys representative protocols that have shaped the field of QKD, focusing on their underlying principles, strengths, and limitations. The aim is to consolidate not only foundational ideas, such as those introduced by BB84 [3], but also more recent experimental advances that extend the scope of secure communication towards satellite-based networks [17], photonic chip integrations [20], and multiparty settings [23].

The evaluation of past and current work enables the identification of gaps and challenges in the area of quantum communication. Historically, each protocol was designed to solve a specific deficiency, such as photon-number splitting attacks [6], detector vulnerabilities [13], or rate-distance limitations [14]. This characteristic sets the stage for proposing DN25 as a unifying protocol, capable of integrating advantages from existing schemes while ensuring context-aware adaptability. A comparative overview of the most relevant quantum cryptography protocols studied, along with their strengths and limitations, is summarized in Table 1.

Classical proposals such as BB84 [3], B92 [2], and E91 [4] laid the foundation of QKD by providing the first examples of secure key sharing through quantum states. BB84, in particular, introduced the principle of encoding information into non-orthogonal states of photons, making it impossible for an eavesdropper to obtain information without disturbing the system and revealing their presence. The B92 protocol simplified the model by using only two states, showing that security could still be maintained with minimal quantum resources, although at the cost of efficiency. Ekert’s protocol (E91) leveraged entanglement and Bell’s theorem, shifting the paradigm from single-photon transmission to correlated pairs, and inspiring later advances in device-independent approaches.

Modern contributions placed emphasis on practical challenges and measurement assumptions. Continuous variable QKD [11] offered compatibility with conventional telecom infrastructures, while DI-QKD [12] and MDI-QKD [13] eliminated trust in devices, significantly strengthening security, although at the cost of experimental demands.

Table 1. Comparative analysis of QKD protocols and DN25

Protocol	Ref.	Year	Strengths	Limitations
BB84	[1]	1984	Foundational QKD, simple implementation	Vulnerable to photon-number attacks with weak sources
B92	[2]	1992	Uses only two nonorthogonal states	Lower key rate, less robust than BB84
E91	[3]	1991	Based on entanglement, strong theoretical foundations	Implementation complex and resource-intensive
BBM92	[4]	1992	Entanglement-based variant of BB84	Sensitive to noise and decoherence
Six-State	[5]	1998	Higher resistance to eavesdropping	Lower efficiency compared to BB84
SARG04	[6]	2004	Robust against photon-number-splitting attacks	Lower key rates than BB84 with decoy states
Decoy-State BB84	[7]	2005	Secure against PNS with weak sources	Requires precise modulation of intensities
DPS-QKD	[8]	2002	No need for PNS countermeasures	Sensitive to phase instability
COW-QKD	[9]	2005	Simple for fiber optic links	Limited security under some side-channel strategies
RR-DPS	[10]	2014	Tolerant against photon-number splittings	Reduced efficiency per transmitted pulse
CV-QKD	[11]	2002	Uses coherent states and standard detectors	Intensive error correction and reconciliation needed
DI-QKD	[12]	2007	Device-independent, does not trust hardware	Highly demanding experimental requirements
MDI-QKD	[13]	2012	Eliminates detector loopholes	Requires complex implementation and synchronization
TF-QKD	[14]	2018	Breaks repeaterless bound, secure long distances	Requires phase stabilization between stations
PM-QKD	[15]	2018	High efficiency through phase matching	Difficult in practical optical fibers
FL-QKD	[16]	2019	High key rates with multiphoton sources	Requires sophisticated hardware
Satellite QKD	[17]	2017	Enables global-scale secure communication	Costly and dependent on line-of-sight conditions
HD-QKD	[20]	2023	Uses high-dimensional states to increase capacity	Experimental complexity and stability issues
Fiber long-distance QKD	[21], [22]	2022 – 2023	Achieved >500 km secure transmission in fiber	Special experimental setups, not yet standard
Multiparty TF-QKD	[23]	2025	Extends TF-QKD to multiparty setups	Coordination challenges in multiuser scenarios
DN25 (this work)	–	2025	Adaptive across QKD/PQC/Hybrid, elastic and context-aware	Conceptual, pending experimental validation

Twin-field QKD [14] and phase-matching QKD [15] pushed distance limits, while floodlight QKD [16] optimized throughput. Satellite-based implementations

[17], high-dimensional schemes [20], and fiber demonstrations beyond 500 km [21], [22] further validated feasibility in real-world conditions. The

multiparty TF-QKD [23] demonstrated progress toward enabling full networked scenarios. Taken together, as summarized in Table 1, these protocols show a strong progression in achieving security, range, and practicality. Yet their solutions remain particular to defined conditions, and none introduces a mechanism for dynamic self-adaptation. DN25 distinguishes itself by proposing a flexible model that integrates QKD, PQC, and hybrid designs into a unified framework, with adaptability as its central contribution. Thus, while prior protocols laid groundwork, DN25 complements the state of the art by bridging the gap between robustness, scalability, and adaptability in quantum-secure communication.

3. Methodology

The The DN25 protocol operates as an adaptive orchestration layer that dynamically combines quantum and post-quantum cryptographic mechanisms. Its operation is governed by contextual awareness, formalized equations, and concrete optimization goals. This section introduces the formal representations used in DN25 and explains the meaning of each variable. The model starts with a context vector that aggregates all relevant state parameters at each decision epoch t:

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} x_{net}(t) \\ x_{dev}(t) \\ x_{sec}(t) \\ x_{app}(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} QBER, loss, SNR, latency, jitter, bandwidth \\ CPU\%, memory, battery, thermal, crypto_{accel} \\ threat_{level}, policy_{criticality}, compliance_{req} \\ data_{rate}, session_{count}, priority_{class} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (1)$$

Here, $x_{net}(t)$ covers network attributes (QBER, packet loss, SNR, latency, jitter, bandwidth). $x_{dev}(t)$ refers to device metrics (CPU usage, memory, battery, thermal conditions, crypto accelerators). $x_{sec}(t)$ expresses the current security posture (threat level, policy criticality, compliance). $x_{app}(t)$ models application constraints (data rate, session count, priority class). Based on this vector, a utility function is computed for each candidate cryptographic scheme:

$$U_k(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \alpha_k^T \mathbf{x}(t) + \beta_k^T g(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \sigma_k S_k(\mathbf{x}(t)) - \eta_k C_k(\mathbf{x}(t)) - \rho_k L_k(\mathbf{x}(t)) - \zeta_k E_k(\mathbf{x}(t)) \quad (2)$$

In this formulation, α_k and β_k are weight vectors for linear and nonlinear terms; $g(\mathbf{x}(t))$ expresses nonlinear engineered features. $S_k(\mathbf{x}(t))$ is the robustness of security, $C_k(\mathbf{x}(t))$ the computational cost, $L_k(\mathbf{x}(t))$ the latency penalty, and $E_k(\mathbf{x}(t))$ the energy

consumption. The scalars σ_k , η_k , ρ_k and ζ_k modulate the impact of each respective factor. An annotated expansion of this same function illustrates explicitly the contribution of each term:

$$U_k(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \overbrace{\alpha_k^T \mathbf{x}(t)}^{\text{linear context fit}} + \overbrace{\beta_k^T g(\mathbf{x}(t))}^{\text{nonlinear features}} + \overbrace{\sigma_k S_k(\mathbf{x}(t))}^{\text{security robustness}} - \overbrace{\eta_k C_k(\mathbf{x}(t))}^{\text{computational cost}} - \overbrace{\rho_k L_k(\mathbf{x}(t))}^{\text{latency penalty}} - \overbrace{\zeta_k E_k(\mathbf{x}(t))}^{\text{energy consumption}} \quad (3)$$

Candidate schemes must respect feasibility requirements, expressed as a set of operational constraints:

$$\begin{cases} \mathcal{L}(a(t), \mathbf{x}(t)) \leq L_{max} & (\text{latency}) \\ \mathcal{S}(a(t), \mathbf{x}(t)) \geq S_{min} & (\text{security}) \\ \mathcal{E}(a(t), \mathbf{x}(t)) \leq E_{max} & (\text{energy}) \\ \mathcal{C}(a(t), \mathbf{x}(t)) \leq C_{max} & (\text{computational}) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Here, $L(a(t), \mathbf{x}(t))$ is the latency that must remain below L_{max} ; $S(a(t), \mathbf{x}(t))$ is the achieved security level that should exceed S_{min} ; $E(a(t), \mathbf{x}(t))$ is the energy usage that must remain below E_{max} ; and $C(a(t), \mathbf{x}(t))$ is the computational cost bounded by C_{max} . With both utilities and constraints defined, the decision engine selects the most appropriate scheme:

$$a^*(t) = \arg \max_{k \in \mathcal{A}_{feas}(\mathbf{x}(t))} \{U_k(\mathbf{x}(t)) - \gamma \Delta(k, a(t-1)) - \nu \mathcal{J}(a(t-1) \rightarrow k)\} \quad (5)$$

In this formula, $\Delta(k, a(t-1))$ denotes the distance or switching cost between the previous scheme and a new candidate. $\mathcal{J}(a(t-1) \rightarrow k)$ is the transition penalty. Parameters γ and ν weigh these factors against the immediate gain. To avoid instability and excessive oscillations, a hysteresis condition is imposed:

$$U_k(\mathbf{x}(t)) > U_{a(t-1)}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \theta_{sw} + \phi \cdot switch_{count}(W) \quad (6)$$

The term θ_{sw} is the minimum threshold that justifies switching, and $\phi \cdot switch_{count}(W)$ limits toggling frequency during a time window W . Beyond short-term utility, DN25 introduces a multi-horizon optimization criterion to minimize long-term risk:

$$\min_{\pi \in \Pi} \mathbb{E}[\sum_{t=1}^T (w_s R_s(a(t)|\mathbf{x}(t)) + w_p R_p(a(t)|\mathbf{x}(t)) + w_e R_e(a(t)|\mathbf{x}(t)) + \lambda \cdot 1_{SLA}(t) + \mu \cdot 1_{SEC}(t) + \gamma \Delta + \nu \mathcal{J})] \quad (7)$$

Here, π is a policy in the set Π ; R_s , R_p , and R_e represent aggregated risks for security, performance, and

efficiency. Weights w_s , w_p , and w_e define their importance. $\lambda \cdot 1_SLA(t)$ and $\mu \cdot 1_SEC(t)$ penalize violations of service or security agreements, while γ and ν account for switching and transition costs. This formulation ensures temporal coherence of cryptographic adaptation. Key generation and distribution are executed via a hybrid derivation function:

$$K_{HYB} = KDF(K_{QKD} \parallel K_{PQC} \parallel ctx \parallel ts) \quad (8)$$

Here, $K-QKD$ is the shared key obtained via QKD, while $K-PQC$ derives from post-quantum algorithms. The parameter ctx denotes contextual identifiers such as session or node, and ts represents a temporal marker or timestamp. The Key Derivation Function (KDF) operation concatenates these elements to produce a hybrid strong key that combines the information-theoretic guarantees of QKD with the resilience of PQC, anchored in specific operational contexts. The complete architecture of DN25 is illustrated in Figure 1. The context monitor captures metrics across network, device, and application layers, and feeds them to the decision engine, which applies the mathematical formulations introduced earlier to enforce utility-driven and constraint-aware choices. Once the selection is made, the execution layer instantiates the chosen schemes and supervises smooth transitions between them to avoid degradation. Finally, KMS is responsible for deriving, authenticating, and securely distributing hybrid keys, while also coordinating refresh and revocation processes.

Figure 1. DN25 Architecture with KMS

The metrics summarized in Table 2 do not represent results from actual experimentation, but instead illustrate parameters that may be monitored and incorporated into

DN25’s decision-making process. These metrics are considered as potential indicators that could be leveraged to assess security posture, operating conditions, and performance trade-offs in real deployments. They are therefore theoretical assumptions, meant to demonstrate how DN25 could balance cryptographic adaptation under diverse contexts.

Table 2. Representative Monitoring and Decision Metrics for DN25

Category	Metric	Symbol	Unit	Threshold
Security	Quantum security level	QSL	bits	≥ 128
Security	Classical security level	CSL	bits	≥ 256
Security	Compromise resilience	KCR	prob.	≥ 0.99
Performance	End-to-end latency	L_{e2e}	ms	≤ 10
Performance	Key generation rate	R_{key}	kbps	≥ 100
Efficiency	Energy per bit	E_{bit}	nJ/bit	≤ 100
Adaptability	Decision latency	L_{dec}	ms	≤ 1
Reliability	Availability	A_{sys}	%	≥ 99.9

4. Discussion of Results

Since At the current stage, DN25 remains a theoretical framework and has not yet been validated in physical testbeds. For this reason, the present section discusses **expected behaviors** derived from the decision model and utility formulations introduced earlier. The emphasis is not on concrete measurements but on the logical consequences of DN25’s adaptation strategy.

Figure 2 illustrates, in simplified form, how DN25 would allocate cryptographic schemes under different contextual scenarios. When network quality is high and the adversarial risk is low (*Scenario A*), QKD is the preferred choice, ensuring low latency and information-theoretic security. Under balanced conditions with moderate risks and resource constraints (*Scenario B*), the adaptive engine converges to a hybrid composition that combines QKD with PQC, achieving elasticity while maintaining operational feasibility. Finally, when the system is exposed to high-threat environments or degraded channels (*Scenario C*), PQC dominates the allocation, prioritizing resilience against

adversarial compromise even at the expense of higher computation.

Figure 2. Theoretical allocation of cryptographic schemes by DN25.

These distributions are, by nature, hypothetical. They were built from the optimization and multi-horizon mechanisms described in Section 3, and they serve to highlight the elastic nature of the orchestration layer: DN25 does not statically commit to a single technology but rebalances its selection depending on security posture, device availability, and communication performance. Future implementations may refine these proportions, but the results already clarify the central principle of DN25: adaptability as a driver of quantum-secure communications in heterogeneous environments.

5. Conclusion

This work introduced **DN25**, an adaptive quantum cryptography protocol designed to integrate QKD, PQC, and hybrid compositions under a unified orchestration framework. The novelty of DN25 lies in its ability to dynamically select and combine cryptographic schemes according to contextual parameters, thus ensuring elasticity across heterogeneous environments. By embedding multi-horizon optimization criteria, monitoring-driven utility functions, and feasibility constraints, DN25 moves beyond the static assumptions of existing QKD protocols and addresses the challenge of adaptability for next-generation quantum communication systems. Another distinctive contribution is the integration of a reinforced KMS, which not only derives hybrid keys but also ensures secure distribution and lifecycle management. The contributions of this study are fourfold: (i) a structured comparative analysis of 20 representative QKD protocols; (ii) the definition of

DN25 as a context-aware cryptographic orchestrator; (iii) the formalization of its decision model through utility and optimization equations; and (iv) an initial theoretical discussion of its behavior, supported by representative scenarios. Together, these contributions bridge the gap between the robustness of quantum security and the flexibility required by real-world applications.

As future work, several directions are envisioned. First, the implementation of DN25 in simulation environments (e.g. NS-3 or QKD network simulators) will validate the decision model and refine the trade-offs among latency, security, and efficiency. Second, testbed evaluation in hybrid infrastructures combining quantum channels and conventional networks will allow for experimental validation of the proposed framework. Third, expanding the protocol to incorporate advanced multi-party and satellite QKD scenarios will extend its scalability toward global quantum networks. Finally, the resilience of DN25 against emerging quantum-enabled adversarial strategies, including side-channel and denial-of-service attacks, remains an important research challenge.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Los autores declaran no tener algún conflicto de interés.

CONTRIBUTION AND APPROVAL OF THE AUTHORS

Darlan Noetzold was responsible for Conceptualization, Methodology and Writing – Original Draft; Juan Francisco de Paz Santana contributed with Validation, Formal Analysis and Writing – Review & Editing; Jorge Luis Victória Barbosa focused on Visualization, Resources and Investigation; and Valderi Reis Quietinho Leithardt contributed with Supervision, Project Administration and Funding Acquisition, respectively. All authors affirm that they have read and approved the final version of this article.

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